

HYDROTECHNICAL STRUCTURES AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article provides a comprehensive overview of the historical, architectural, engineering, and environmental aspects of water structures in Uzbekistan, with a particular focus on the iconic city of Samarkand. It examines the evolution of hydrotechnical engineering practices in the region, highlighting the intricate designs and technological innovations of ancient civilizations. By synthesizing insights from diverse disciplines, including history, architecture, engineering, and environmental science, the article offers valuable insights into the cultural significance, technical functionality, and ecological impacts of water management systems in Uzbekistan. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of sustainable development and the preservation of hydrotechnical heritage for future generations.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, Water structures, Hydrotechnical engineering, Samarkand, Architectural heritage, Ancient civilizations, Water management, Reservoirs, Canal systems, Environmental impacts, Cultural significance, Engineering marvels, Historical monuments, Sustainable development, Climatic conditions, Geographical features, Socio-economic implications, Ecological sustainability, Hydraulic dynamics, Technological advancements.*

Introduction. Uzbekistan, with its unique climatic conditions and geographical setting, has long relied on intricate water management systems to sustain its agricultural endeavors. Nestled within this landscape lies the historic city of Samarkand, its architectural narrative intricately intertwined with centuries of hydraulic engineering feats. These water structures not only reflect a mastery of construction materials and techniques but also showcase the profound knowledge our ancestors possessed in the domains of hydrotechnics and hydromechanics.

The climatic conditions and geographical location of Uzbekistan require farming using water structures and canals. The architectural history of Samarkand has been formed in its own way for many years. Along with land structures, hydrotechnical structures have gained great importance in the history of human development. The results of the study of construction materials, mathematical and architectural solutions and constructions of historical water structures that have been preserved in the territory of our republic show that the masters of water management and agricultural masters of that time had strong knowledge in the field of hydrotechnics and hydromechanics. Hydrotechnical structures are structures built to use water resources or to combat the erosive effects of water. H. e., according to its function, is divided into 2 groups - general and special facilities. H. e. includes water dispenser, water intake, water disposal and water adjustment facilities. Water drops (dams) create differences in water pressure or water level in front of and behind the structure. Water receiver structures serve to drain water from the source (river, lake, reservoir, etc.) into channels. Aqueduct (vodovod) is built in order to direct water to appropriate places (canal, channel, aqueduct, duiker, pipes, hydraulic tunnels); connecting structures (downspouts, water heaters, gutters, channel adjusters). H. e. ensures smooth integration of different parts. Water disposal facilities serve to remove excess water from reservoirs, canals,

pressure basins. In order to adjust the amount of water to be discharged, valves are installed in water discharge facilities. Diverter structures are designed to change and improve the natural conditions of water flow, to protect riverbeds and banks from being washed away, from accumulation of liquid, from the effects of ice, etc. Special H. e. includes hydropower (hydroelectric power station buildings, pressure basins, etc.), water transport (ship berths, locks, wharves, etc.) facilities, reclamation (main and distribution canals, pumping station for raising water to the required height, collector-drainage network, clarifier , water distributors, water measuring devices, etc.) structures, water supply and sewage facilities, etc.

H.e. are divided into main (dams, pressure walls, spillways, straightening structures, tunnels, etc.) and auxiliary structures (ice protection structures, separation walls, etc.) according to their function. H.e. is divided into 4 levels according to capital (4 levels include auxiliary facilities). In accordance with the adopted level of capital, the strength level of H. e. differs from other engineering structures in that it is under the influence of constantly flowing or standing water. Mechanical (statistical and dynamic load, pressure of water during an earthquake, filtration pressure, ice pressure, erosive effect of fluids, etc.), physical and chemical (rusting of materials, dissolution of salts in the ground, high speed and vacuum, etc.), have a biological (grass growth, etc.) effect. Therefore, in construction of H.e. hard materials, such as special hydraulic concrete, reinforced concrete, etc. are used. H.e. uses modern automation and telemechanics.

Reservoir is an open-air storage area (usually formed by rock or earthworks) where water is collected and stored in usable quantities. Reservoirs are an important feature of many water supply systems in the world. Climate change causes the natural flow of rivers and streams to change significantly over time. Periods of extreme flow and valley flooding may alternate with low flow or drought. Therefore, the role of reservoirs is to store water during periods of high flow, thus preventing flood disasters, and then allow the gradual release of water during periods of low flow. Common reservoirs have probably been created throughout human history to provide water for drinking and irrigation. From South Asia and North Africa, the use of reservoirs spread to Europe and other continents.

Reservoirs are usually created by building dams across rivers, but non-channel reservoirs can be provided by aqueducts and canals or pipes that transfer water from the river to natural or artificial depressions.

If the flow of water is blocked in the reservoir, the flow rate will decrease and the sediment will accumulate. Thus, streams that carry a lot of suspended sediment are poor places for reservoirs. Turbidity rapidly reduces storage capacity and dramatically shortens the useful life of a small reservoir. Even in larger water bodies, sedimentation is a common and serious problem. Because removal of accumulated sediment from reservoirs is usually too expensive to be practical, sediment-filled in-stream reservoirs provide a reserve of storage capacity to compensate for depletions caused by sedimentation. However, most reservoirs do not have a life expectancy of more than 100 years at current sediment levels. A related problem is erosion of the stream channel beneath the reservoir when water is released. As the sediment load accumulates in the reservoir, the carrying capacity of the released water is renewed and causes channel erosion.

Reservoir water can be lost through surface evaporation, percolation into the surrounding soil or bedrock, and through percolation through the foundation of the dam. Leakage losses can usually be reduced, but evaporation losses often have major consequences. In temperate and tropical climates, gross evaporation from the water table can be several meters per year. In humid

regions, this loss is compensated by direct precipitation, and the net surface loss may be moderate or negligible. In low-precipitation areas, net loss can be significant, 1.5 meters (5 ft) or more per year in some desert areas. There are several physical, chemical, and biological methods to reduce evaporation from reservoirs, each with its own advantages and disadvantages. Floating or suspended covers can save a large percentage of water, but are impractical or too expensive for large reservoirs. Chemical treatments are widely used to reduce evaporation rates, but they require frequent reapplication and do not significantly reduce water loss. Biological methods include windbreaks and floating plants and can significantly reduce evaporation, but their use is limited to reservoirs with favorable conditions.

Watersheds range in size and complexity from small single-purpose reservoirs to large and complex multi-purpose reservoirs. A single-purpose reservoir is designed to perform only one function, such as irrigation, hydropower generation, navigation, flood control, water supply, recreation, or low-flow regulation. There was a tendency to build multi-purpose reservoirs designed to perform at least two main functions.

Reservoirs can have negative environmental impacts, such as destroying fish habitats and ecosystems – and large reservoir projects can require prevention of flooding of cities and towns. For example, the construction of three gorge dams on China's Yangtze River (Chang Jiang), designed primarily as a source of flood control and electricity, displaced nearly two million people. Social and environmental impacts should be taken into account in the planning stages of the construction of new reservoirs. Relatively small indoor reservoirs are familiar sights in most towns and cities. These reservoirs, often built on hills or supported by steel tanks on towers, are an integral part of many local water distribution systems. They usually provide a storage capacity equal to the community's average water demand for one day. Tanks are elevated to ensure sufficient water pressure in the pipes. Water is used for emergency situations such as power outages, pump station failures and fire control. In addition, these reservoirs serve to meet the peak hourly water demand of the community. When the demand for water exceeds the average daily demand, water flows from the reservoirs into the distribution network.

Conclusion. From the ancient canals of Samarkand to the modern reservoirs dotting our landscapes, Uzbekistan's journey through time is mirrored in its water structures. As we continue to harness and innovate within the realm of hydrotechnical engineering, it is imperative to acknowledge the multifaceted roles these structures play—from mitigating flood risks to sustaining agricultural livelihoods. Moving forward, the preservation of our water heritage and the conscientious development of new reservoirs must harmonize with environmental and social considerations, ensuring a sustainable legacy for generations to come.

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